

MANAGEMENT OF DEEP STERNAL WOUND INFECTION

ЛІКУВАННЯ ГЛИБОКОЇ ХВОРОБИ РАНИ ГРУДИНИ

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Purpose. Deep sternal wound infection (DSWI) is a rare but potentially devastating complication in cardiac surgery in patients undergoing Median Sternotomy. In this work, we tried to explore current treatment options for DSWI.

Materials and methods. Updated protocols from Royal Papworth on Infection Control and Tissue Viability were reviewed. In addition, a literature review of NICE Guidelines and PubMed Was performed.

Study. Management of DSWI can be complex and often requires a multidisciplinary team approach involving infectious disease specialists, microbiologists, Wound Management Team, and even cardiothoracic and plastic surgeons in more complicated cases. Early detection, appropriate antibiotic treatment, aggressive surgical debridement, and use of regional muscle flaps have significantly improved treatment outcomes and have shown promising results.

Sternal Wound was first classified into three types based on timing and presentation by Pairolero and Arnold in 1984³. Rupperecht et al (2013)¹ further classified sternal complications into superficial and deep sternal wound infections with or without sternal instability.

The contributing factors for DSWI development can be broadly divided into two categories, Patient-related and Surgical related.³

While Deep sternal wound infection with sternal instability is associated with the highest morbidity and mortality, DSWI can occur without sternal instability in patients with impaired wound healing in an area of excessive. Soft tissue tension and tight closure.

Once the infection has developed deep in the sternum, there can be oozing from the surgical site, along with unexplained fever with or without sternal instability. Patients often complain of constant sternal pain which worsens on movement.

Once deep wound infection is suspected patient needs to be cultured to detect the causative organism. Patients are then started on broad-spectrum IV antibiotics until culture results are available. Thereafter, the dose and antibiotics can be adjusted in collaboration with a microbiologist. Patients also will need to undergo CT scan to determine the depth and extent of the infection, and also exclude osteomyelitis and

bone fragmentation. Based on the CT scan and response to the Antibiotic Therapy, a multi-disciplinary team involving the Surgical Team, Radiologists, Microbiologists, Medical Team, and Pharmacists make the decision whether to continue with conservative Medical management or to proceed with the surgical management and its extent².

If the Conservative Medical Therapy is opted for, the Patient remains in the hospital and the Antibiotic therapy will be adjusted based on the wound culture results and sensitivity, clinical response as well as complications that may occur during the treatment.

In case of wound dehiscence, Vacuum Assisted therapy is started to improve granulation tissue growth and also to reduce infection from spreading. Vacuum-Assisted Therapy has shown great results in treating non-healing wounds and Sternal wounds and has become an integrative part of the dehisced sternal wound therapy⁴.

In case these measures fail to tackle the infection, Surgical debridement and in severe cases, sternal reconstruction using titanium plates is required. In case of a soft-tissue defect, after debridement, local or free flaps are raised by plastic surgeons to fix the soft tissue defects and close the wound.

Conclusion. Deep Sternal Wound infection remains one of the challenges of postoperative patient care after Midline Osteotomy. The mainstay of treatment is the prevention of infection by identifying and addressing the risk factors. Culture Sensitive Antibiotic Therapy and VAC Therapy play a crucial role in the treatment of Deep Sternal Wound Infection. If the infection persists despite optimized medical management, the Surgical Debridement, along with Sternal Reconstruction needs to be considered.

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